

SELECTION PROCEDURE AND ONBOARDING
CRITERIA FOR AGRIFOODTEF CUSTOMERS
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Dissemination Level

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Document Revision History

Date	Issue	Author/Editor/Contributor	Summary of main change
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25/07/2023	V01	PSG review	Changes from partners feedback
28/09/2023	V02	FBK team	Final version

Executive summary

This document describes the Onboarding Procedures to be followed in AgrifoodTEF to enable the provision of services. The step-by-step procedure is meant to assist Consortium Members in the process of assessing whether a third-party organisation, external to the project, satisfies the requirements for accessing an AgrifoodTEF service. This results in the selection of candidate customers being regulated by clear rules.

1. AgrifoodTEF High Level Procedure and Onboarding Tasks

Figure 1 - Onboarding overall process

The AgrifoodTEF project has been created to provide test and experimenting services to all those organisations that work on AI and Robotics solutions for the agrifood sector and that need support. Figure 1 represents the overall flow-chart diagram regulating the onboarding procedure for service delivery within AgrifoodTEF.

Onboarding concerns the first part of the full service interaction cycle, from processing a Service Request to the stage where the TEF team and the correspondent customer representative start the Service Planning part, which is out of scope for the Onboarding procedure and to be managed by the Partner(s) appointed as contractor(s) for the execution of the envisaged AgrifoodTEF service.

AgrifoodTEF website publishes a catalogue of services available from the Partners that are member of the Consortium. This catalogue, duly versioned in its releases for ease of referencing, will be continuously updated throughout the project execution and will be the first port of call for potential AgrifoodTEF Customers, who will be able to see what is on offer and who to engage with in order to proceed with their service request, produced at first in a free text format.

Following such first interaction, the following step consists of filling in a Service Request form, highlighting the path through the Service Catalogue hierarchy leading to the required service (see further details in Section 3.2 below). This request will be sent from a AgrifoodTEF Customer to an AgrifoodTEF Lead Partner, highlighted in the Catalogue as the Partner representative for the service of interest. If a specific Catalogue Service is not quite what is expected, we envisage the opportunity to negotiate the content of the existing or creating a new Service (related to the one identified) that the Customer would like to see executed. The opportunity given to potential customers to specify themselves a tailored service building on what they find in the Catalogue is the means through which we want to

reach the right balance between what is on offer and what the market needs, especially in the preliminary phase of project execution.

The next step is an assessment of the request from the Lead Partner who validates the feasibility within the AgrifoodTEF scope and the availability of the needed resources. This check is to be done individually by the Lead Partner if it is to become the sole contractor; otherwise it must involve other Partners if some level of support is needed. Once this step is executed, the Lead Partner (representing itself or a group of Partners) forwards the related documentation (service request description and auto-certification on the State-Aid matters) to the Onboarding Committee for their evaluation. Should additional info be requested, the OC declines the request and it becomes care of the Lead Partner to address the comments and procure the requested additional info before resubmitting.

2. Eligibility Check Process for Customer Onboarding

The figure below illustrates further details of the eligibility checks of the onboarding process to be managed by the AgrifoodTEF Onboarding Committee (AFT OC), which is represented by the members of the Project Steering Group, where each Country represented in the Consortium has one representative through the Node or Satellite Leader.

Figure 2 - Eligibility check process

Following interactions between customer and the identified Lead Partner, the Service Request Description is drafted and sent to the AFT OC members who can individually express their evaluation, for a timeframe of 5 working days. If a more detailed discussion is required, the AFT OC includes the case in the following fortnightly meeting (online). If the OC raises no concerns, the request is to be considered approved.

2.1. Technical eligibility

This formal check concerns the *technical eligibility of the request* and is in place to ensure that the services being delivered by the AgrifoodTEF meet the target objectives of the project. More specifically the AFT OC must ensure that the solutions proposed by the AgrifoodTEF Customers have indeed a valid target for their AI related components or indeed fall into the category of Robotics. Either (or both) of these conditions must be verified to get the go-ahead together with ensuring that such solutions meant to exploit validation services have been created for the agrifood sector.

2.2. State-Aid and administrative eligibility

Besides falling into the right category for technical eligibility, Service Request Descriptions must also fulfil *administrative eligibility*. This is a process that depends on the nature of the co-funding, which in principle might differ amongst different node and satellite Countries when it comes to the related obligations imposed by it. The minimal conditions to satisfy at European level are:

- To be officially recognized as a SME
- To have State Aid availability
- To fulfil local regulations for the granting of State Aid

The lead partner bears responsibility for validating the State Aid obligations listed above according to the national regulations on the matter.

This step is needed to ensure there is capacity to support the delivery of the service through State Aid.

2.3. Eligibility extension – Financial capacity

Catalogue services will have a nominal price indication , which will be based on the expected use of facilities resources and manpower engagement.

Eligible customers can use State Aid to partially pay for the full service price, provided that they have finances to cover for the remainder. Alternatively, they can pay the full price if State Aid is not to be used.

Worth mentioning that the AgrifoodTEF “service delivery through State Aid” will progressively leave place to more business oriented types of relationships between AgrifoodTEF and its customers. At the start of the agrifoodTEF project it will be possible for nodes and satellites to deliver services with a maximum 100% discount, leveraging State Aid mechanism within the stated rules of onboarding. As the project execution progresses, it is expected the discount will be progressively reduced, implying that the AgrifoodTEF customers will have to pay themselves part or whole of the service price for an amount which is then to be excluded from the State-Aid accounting. With the *technical eligibility* being the same as before the *administrative eligibility* checks here are more related to the suitability of the offer and the willingness to pay from the customer perspective.

3. Service Feasibility Process for Customer Onboarding

With the eligibility checks being resolved, at this point the emphasis will shift to the preparation of the Service Agreement which directly engages the Lead Partner and the AgrifoodTEF Customer in a negotiation phase that concludes with the settlement of the final service agreement.

This is the phase where an assessment of needed resources and final service price are to be made by the Lead Partner to ensure the onboarding procedure can be concluded.

3.1. AgrifoodTEF Service customization

We mentioned before a situation where the identified Catalogue Service needs some adjustments to better meet customers’ expectations and / or a situation where a deeper assessment of intended service objectives require additional Partners engagement. This is allowed within the onboarding process with the only attention to be paid to the need of updating the Public Catalogue of Services if any of those adjustments during the negotiation phase bring different flavour to the description of the service to be used which was selected in the first instance.

Figure 3 - Service list and catalogue revisions

At this point the service execution can start according to the stated deliverables in the Service Agreement. From that moment onwards the project is included in the due diligence monitoring pipeline until delivery.

4. Documentation

4.1. Onboarding specific documents and forms

A summary of the documents and processes listed above can be seen in the figure below, coupling input documents to expected validations and timelines

Figure 4 - Documents and validation rounds

4.2. Customer Service Tracking from onboarding to service delivery

To guarantee monitoring of all AgrifoodTEF processes and of project KPI progress there is the need to maintain a detailed log of activities performed for service delivery to all AgrifoodTEF customers.

The following table summarizes at high level all documents and information that has to be tracked and maintained by all AgrifoodTEF nodes when onboarding and delivering AgrifoodTEF services. This section is indicative and it will be subject of more precise investigation as part of the WP4 activities that have to harmonise procedures and protocols of engagement at AgrifoodTEF level.

The information on all AgrifoodTEF services being delivered has to be managed within some sort of Customer Relationship Management tool for the whole AgrifoodTEF, so to allow the whole monitoring of progress of project KPIs and to keep track and report all delivered services. The following table provides some information on what is to be procured at what step by whom.

Process Phase	Documents/Information to be maintained	Document Producers
Eligibility of Customer and Service Request	• Customer description and references	Leading partner (from contact form)
	• Service Request form	Leading Partner + Customer
	• SME Declaration	Customer
	• State Aid Capacity assessment	Customer

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> National specific documentation required 	Customer
Service Feasibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Service Decomposition (from catalogue), involved partners and cost estimates 	Leading Partner + other involved partners
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Customer Service Agreement 	Leading Partner + other involved partners
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> NDA (optional) 	Customer + all involved partners
Service Planning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Service Delivery Plan (timing & resources) 	Leading partner
Service Execution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Delivery Plan Tracking 	All involved partners
Service Reporting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Service Delivery Report 	All involved partners

5. Mapping of Service Request on AgrifoodTEF Service catalogue – an example

High level description of service by customer has to be mapped onto one or a set of services predefined in the service catalogue. Let’s follow an example of a contact from an SME to a Node in the AgrifoodTEF:

Company XXX has developed a hardware and software solution that leverages on AI algorithms to analyse productivity of field production for YYYY crop. The company is interested in getting support in the execution of the following testing and validation activity of its product:

- HW benchmarking of the developed solution using different video cameras that can be part of the product configuration in real field conditions;*
- management and organization of datasets collected from the field for their processing and further visualization;*
- Comparison of developed and patented algorithms with alternative state of the art solutions to get metrics on quality and performance of the applied solution.*

The above described “Service Request” has to be mapped onto the existing AgrifoodTEF catalogue. The procedure for assigning the customer's service request to the services listed in the agrifoodTEF service catalogue can be described as follows:

The agrifoodTEF service catalogue is structured by a set of categorizations. These categorizations consist of a set of categories that also serve as tags or labels to describe the services. To map a customer's service request, the appropriate categories of the different categorizations have to be selected. The customer is then presented with a short list of all relevant services in the catalogue that correspond to the selected categories. From this list, the most suitable services for the customer can be selected, or a compilation of several services can be created that most closely matches the customer's needs.

For the introduced example above the set of selected categories can look like (selected items are marked with an 'X'):

Service categorization input form

Sector	User Need	Location
<p><i>What are you interested in your product / solution in?</i></p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Arable Farming <input type="checkbox"/> Viticulture <input type="checkbox"/> Horticulture <input type="checkbox"/> Livestock farming <input type="checkbox"/> Greenhouse <input type="checkbox"/> Food processing <input type="checkbox"/> Tree crops <input type="checkbox"/> Not relevant (explain)</p>	<p><i>What can Agrifood TEF help you with?</i></p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Desk assessment <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Test design <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Test Setup <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Test execution <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Collection of test data <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Performance evaluation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Provision of datasets <input type="checkbox"/> Data augmentation <input type="checkbox"/> Data analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Certification <input type="checkbox"/> ELSA assessment <input type="checkbox"/> LCA assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Conformity assessment <input type="checkbox"/> AI model training <input type="checkbox"/> People Training <input type="checkbox"/> Business modelling <input type="checkbox"/> Market research <input type="checkbox"/> Not relevant (explain)</p>	<p><i>Where should Agrifood TEF deliver?</i></p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> At user's premises <input type="checkbox"/> Italy <input type="checkbox"/> Germany <input type="checkbox"/> Belgium <input type="checkbox"/> Netherlands <input type="checkbox"/> Austria <input type="checkbox"/> France <input type="checkbox"/> Poland <input type="checkbox"/> Sweden <input type="checkbox"/> Spain <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Not relevant</p>
Deliverable to TEF		
<p><i>What to test / evaluate / validate?</i></p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Physical system <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Software or AI model <input type="checkbox"/> Data <input type="checkbox"/> Design / Documentation <input type="checkbox"/> Other (explain)</p>		

Figure 5 - Service categorization form

This leads to a short list of 12 services out of more than 150 initial services of the agrifoodTEF service catalogue. An excerpt of that short list is shown in the figure below.

Service ID	Name of Service	Description of Service	Sector	Deliverable to TEF	User need	Location	offered by	contact
BE_004	Fertilizer spreader for arable farming: calibration based on vision and AI-methods	Perform fertilizer spreader calibration based on camera detection/vision and AI-methods using a mobile set-up, for spreader manufacturers	arable farming	physical system (possibly including software)	test design, test setup, test execution, collection of test data	in Belgium	ILVO	Jordy.Windels@ilvo.vlaanderen.be
BE_007	Robotic Software Framework for arable farming	Application and deployment of agricultural robotic software framework	arable farming	physical system (possibly including software)	test design, test setup, test execution, performance evaluation	in Belgium	ILVO	Jordy.Windels@ilvo.vlaanderen.be
SE_017	Validation of work result under real conditions crop production robotics	The innovation is tested in real work or real work-like conditions in the nordics and the work result is evaluated from a potential customers point of view. The service is adapted to the actual innovation to be tested.	arable farming	physical system (possibly including software), software	test design, test setup, test execution, collection of test data, performance evaluation	in Sweden	RISE	jonas.engstrom@ri.se
SE_018	Validation of work result under real conditions crop production sensors and decision support systems	The innovation is tested in real work or real work-like conditions in the nordics and the work result is evaluated from a potential customers point of view. The service is adapted to the actual innovation to be tested.	arable farming	physical system (possibly including software), software	test design, test setup, test execution, collection of test data, performance evaluation	in Sweden	RISE	jonas.engstrom@ri.se
SE_019	Validation of work result under real conditions crop production UAV	The innovation is tested in real work or real work-like conditions in the nordics and the work result is evaluated from a potential customers point of view. The service is adapted to the actual innovation to be tested.	arable farming	physical system (possibly including software), software	test design, test setup, test execution, collection of test data, performance evaluation	in Sweden	RISE	jonas.engstrom@ri.se
AT_014	testing of biomass estimation	testing the accuracy of a system to estimate biomass	arable farming	physical system (possibly including software)	test design, test setup, test execution, collection of test data, performance evaluation	in Austria	JR	agrifoodtef@josephinum.at
FR_010	Characterization of Smart systems for weed destruction	Development in progress of a bench able to evaluate : i/ All Perception/Decision modules ii/ all Perception/Decision/Action Modules	arable farming	physical system (possibly including software), software	test design, test setup, test execution, collection of test data, performance evaluation	in France	INRAE-TSCF-AgroTechnoPôle	
FR_013	Evaluation of Automatic Machines and Agricultural robots	Physical tests for performance qualification of IA (or classical) Perception/Control/Command systems in flat and slope areas controlled conditions and with high dynamic localisation reference measurement system	arable farming	physical system (possibly including software)	test design, test setup, test execution, collection of test data, performance evaluation	in France	INRAE-TSCF-	

Figure 6 - Excerpt of a short list out of the service catalogue

Since the Lead Partner and contact persons are listed for all services, as illustrated above the customer can contact the service providers directly to arrange for the use a service. In turn, the agrifoodTEF network can also help to put together service packages for customers that include services from several partners.

Here follows an example on how the mapping for the service example requested by AgrifoodTEF customer can be decomposed:

Service ID	Name of Service	Service Description	Potential Partner for service delivery	Cost estimates (according to catalogue)
BE_001		Provide a local AI-Testfield to develop and test autonomous robots and AI-based systems.		45Keuro
S02	WP1 - physical	Physical Edge-HW Benchmark		15Keuro

Example data

S03	WP2 - Digital	Datasets - Quality Assessment		45Keuro
S04	WP2 - Digital	AI Integration - Model Improvement / Adaptation		25 Keuro
Total estimates				130 Keuro

In the case where the service is not present in AgrifoodTEF service catalogue a negotiation phase (as illustrated earlier) will be initiated and will result in a catalogue extension and update following the Onboarding Committee positive assessment.

